

Svara Varisai-s in Saṅgīta Pradāyini

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Abstract:

The Tradition of Indian classical music has been exhaustively preserved and documented in the form of manuscripts, treatises, publications, translations, and commentaries written over centuries. These sources trace the historical evolution of various musical concepts and practices, providing invaluable insights in diverse languages such as Sanskrit, Tamil, Telugu, Kannada, Malayalam, Marathi and so on. One such work written in Telugu language is ‘Saṅgīta Pradāyini’. Saṅgīta Pradāyini is an early music publication which contains theoretical and practical aspects of Karṇāṭaka music.

The current article mainly focuses on the basic and advance svara exercises given in the publication, ‘Saṅgīta Pradāyini’.

Keywords: Publications, Sangita Pradayini, Svara, Tala, Exercise, Tana.

Introduction

In Indian classical music, there are many texts that are documented and preserved for many centuries. There are many manuscripts, treatises, publications and other books in the languages- Telugu, Samskr̥ta, Tamiẓ Kaṇṇaḍa, Maḷayāḷam and so on which covers various topics, methods and other aspects in the music.

Indian classical music is categorized into two types, namely Karṇāṭaka music and Hindusthānī music. Hindusthānī music has the musical forms such as Bandiṣ, Dhrupad, Ṭhumrī and other forms. Karṇāṭaka music includes musical forms such as Gīta, Svarajati, Varṇa, Kṛti, Kīrtana, Aṣṭapadi, Pada, Jāvali and so on.

In both, Karṇāṭaka and Hindusthānī music, there are fundamental exercises which are very helpful for a music student to improve their range, tempo, pitch, svara position, control over the voice and other techniques. These exercises also play a significant role in the Instrumental playing techniques.

There are some exercises in Hindusthānī music under the section called ‘Alankār’ also known as Palṭa-s and different types of tān.

Similarly, In Karṇāṭaka music, Svarāvaḷi, Jaṅṭa varisai, Dāṭu varisai, Alaṅkāra-s, Mēlsthāyi and kīṅsthāyi varisai and other svara exercises are taught to the students as basic lessons. Karṇāṭaka music can be understood under 2 aspects: Abhyāsa gāna and Sabhā gāna.

Abhyāsa gāna includes the basic level of exercises like Saraḷi varisai, Jaṅṭa varisai, Mēl sthāyi, Kīṅ sthāyi and other musical forms such as Gīta, Svarapallavi and so on, which are bound to be practiced.

Sabhā gāna includes the forms that are suitable for performing. Varṇa, kṛti, kīrtana, Pada, Jāvaḷi, Tillāna and so on come under the category, Sabhā gāna.

Under Abhyāsa gāna, the basic exercises are taught to the beginners in their initial level of learning. The basic exercises are given in the early music publications where the lessons for beginners, intermediate and advanced levels are explained. There are some advance exercises which include manōdharma aspects like Varisai-s having tāna, Ciṭṭa tāna-s, pre-notated Kalpana svara-s and so on.

In the Pre-1940 music publications, aspects like basic and advance exercises, rāga, tāna, 72 mēḷakarta system, notations for the kṛti-s and kīrtana-s of various composers and many rarely known concepts are specified.

There are many manuscripts, publications and other books which deal with the different types of exercises that are usually not seen in the present day's basic exercises. Gānāmṛta bōdhini (1953) of A.S.Pañcāpakēśa ayyar mentions a limited number of basic exercises which has become a source of learning for the beginners in the present day. The beginner level students are introduced to Svarāvaḷi varusalu which are generally known as Saraḷivarisai-s and the other foundational exercises namely, Jaṅṭa varisai-s, Heccu sthāyi, Taggu sthāyi, Dāṭu varisai-s and Alaṅkāra-s are also taught.

The main focus of the article is on the basic and advance exercises given in the publication called 'Saṅgīta Pradāyini'.

Saṅgīta Pradāyini:

Saṅgīta Pradāyini is one of the earliest music publications in Telugu language, authored by K.Varadācāriar, K,V.Śrīnivāsa ayyaṅgār and K.Kṛṣṇamācāriar, in the year 1916. K.Varadācāriar, popularly known as Tiger Varadācāriar, is a musician and musicologist (1876); his brothers K.V. Śrīnivāsa ayyaṅgār is a musicologist, K.Kṛṣṇamācāriar is a vīṇa player. Apart from Saṅgīta Pradāyini, they are known to have authored the works Saṅgīta Citrāmbari, Saṅgīta pradāyini, Ādi Saṅgīta Ratnāvaḷi, Ādi Śrī Tyāgaraja Hṛdayam, Gānabōdhini, Saṅgīta Cintāmaṇi, Saṅgīta Rasārṇavam, Gāna Bhāskaramu and other works.

The publication Saṅgīta Pradāyini consists of the theoretical part - Svāra prakaraṇa, Rāga prakaraṇa and Tāḷa prakaraṇa, collectively named as 'Lakṣaṇa saṅgraha'.

- Svāra prakaraṇa gives brief definitions for Svāra, details of Prakṛti and Vikṛti svāra-s, Sthāyi and Svārasthāna-s on Vīṇa.

- In tāla prakaraṇa, details of Tāla śabdōtpatti, Tālavasyakam, Tālōtpatti, Kālakriya māna-s, Tāla matamulu, Tāla daśa prāna-s, Tāla śadānga chakra, 35 Sūlādi tāla-s table, Trikāla-s are mentioned.
- In Rāga prakaraṇa, definitions for Rāgaśabdhārdham, Rāga-s, Sampūrṇa, Śāḍava, Auḍava and Vakra raga-s are given precisely.
- Apart from this, the method of 72 mēlakarta rāga-s, their names with svarasthāna-s and Kaṭapayādi saṅkhyā sūtra are mentioned.

This is followed by the practical part which has been divided into Prathama bhāga and Dvītīya bhāga.

A. Prathama bhāga – 1st part:

It is further classified into 11 chapters:

1. Svarāvaḷi
2. Heccusthāyivarusalu
3. Jaṅṭa varusalu
4. Dāṭu varusalu
5. Alaṅkāra-s in 35 tāla-s
6. Piḷḷāri gītālu
7. Gītamulu
8. Svarajatulu
9. Ciṭṭa tānālu
10. Tāna varṇamulu
11. Aṭa tāla varṇamulu

B. Dvītīya bhāga – 2nd part:

1. Tyāgaraja svāmi kīrtanalu
2. Dīkṣita kīrtanalu
3. Paṭnam Subrahmaṇya kīrtanalu

Exercises in Saṅgīta Pradāyini:

1. Svarāvaḷi:

Svarāvaḷi is given in Mālavagaṅḷa rāga with the scale ‘s r g m p d n ś - ś n d p m g r s’ in Caturaśra jāti Tripuṭa tāḷa under 3 sections. There are a total of 32 varisai-s given in 3 sections in which the first section gives 16 varisai-s, second section gives 6 varisai-s and the third section gives 10 varisai-s.

Section – I (16 varisai-s):

Over a period of time, Svarāvaḷi have been restricted to a limit of 14 varisai-s which are commonly practiced as given in Gānāmṛta bōdhini of A.S.Pañcāpakēśa ayyar. The Svarāvaḷi exercises which are common in both Saṅgīta Pradāyini and Gānāmṛta bōdhini are:

Serial no.	Svarāvaḷi
1.	s r g m p d n ś ś n d p m g r s
2.	s r s r - s r g m s r g m p d n ś ś n ś n - ś n d p ś n d p m g r s
6.	s r g m - p d s r s r g m p d n ś ś n d p - m g ś n ś n d p m g r s
9.	s r g m - p m d p s r g m p d n ś ś n d p - m p g m ś n d p m g r s
13.	s r g r g , g m p m p , d p d , m p d p d n d p m p d p m g r s

The exercises that are different from the contemporary practice of Svarāvaḷi exercises have been illustrated below:

Serial no.	Svarāvaḷi
3.	s r g s - r s r g - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d ś - n ś n d - ś n d p - m g r s -
4.	s r g m - s r s r - s r g m - s r g m - ś n d p - ś n ś n - ś n d p - m g r s -

5.	s r g m - p s r g - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d p - m ś n d - ś n d p - m g r s -
7.	s r g r - s r s r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d n - ś n ś n - ś n d p - m g r s -
8.	s r g m - s r s r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d p - ś n ś n - ś n d p - m g r s -
10.	s r s r - g r s r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n ś n - d n ś n - ś n d p - m g r s -
11.	s r g r - g m g r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d n - d p d n - ś n d p - m g r s -
12.	s r s r - s r g r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n ś n - d p d n - ś n d p - m g r s -
14.	s r g r - g r s r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d ś - n d ś n - ś n d p - m g r s -
15.	s r g r - g r s r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d n - d n ś n - ś n d p - m g r s -
16.	s r g m - g m g r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n d p - d p d n - ś n d p - m g r s -

- It is understood that the section focuses on the linear svara patterns.
- In the pūrvāṅga section, the phrase "s r s r s r g m" from the 2nd varisai is structurally identical to the latter half of the 8th varisai, "s r g m s r s r", and vice versa—demonstrating a reversal in the order of phrases.
- A few varisai-s exhibit the repeated patterns “s r s r” in the pūrvāṅga and “ś n ś n” in the uttarāṅga
- As per the notation, the varisai-s are grouped in the pattern of ‘4+4’, however some of the varisai-s can be interpreted by developing various combinational patterns, highlighting the accent points at different places.

For example:

a) Third varisai:

s r g s - r s r g - 1231- 2123

ś n d ś - n ś n d - 8768- 7876

s r g - s r - s r g - 123-12-123 in the ascent and ś n d - ś n - ś n d - 876-87-876

in the descent.

b) Fifth varisai:

s r g m - p s r g - 1234 - 5123

ś n d p - m ś n d - 8765-4876

s r g m p - s r g - 12345-123 in the ascent and ś n d p m-ś n d - 87654-876 in

the descent.

c) Tenth varisai:

s r s r - g r s r - 1212- 3212

ś n ś n - d n ś n - 8787 - 6787

s r - s r g - r s r – 12-123-212 in the ascent and ś n ś n d - n ś n – 87-876-787 in the descent.

Section – II (6 Varisai-s):

This segment includes 6 varisai-s.

Serial no.	Svarāvaḷi
17.	s r s g - r g r m - s r g m - p d n ś - ś n ś d - n d n p - ś n d p - m g r s -

- The pūrvāṅga of the varisai is same as the first line of the 1st dāṭu varisai in the ascent and descent.

Serial no.	Svarāvaḷi
18.	s g r m - g r g s - s r g m - p d n ś - ś d n p - d n d ś - ś n d p - m g r s -
19.	s m g m - r g s r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś p d p - n d ś n - ś n d p - m g r s -
20.	s m g m - p g m r - s r g m - p d n ś - ś p d p - m d p n - ś n d p - m g r s -
21.	s m g p - m d p n - s r g m - p d n ś - ś p n m - p r m s - ś n d p - m g r s -
22.	s m r p - m r p ś - s r g m - p d n ś - ś p n m - p r m s - ś n d p - m g r s -

- The 21st varisai presents a deliberate combination of alternating svāra-s between the first and second āvarta-s. The phrases “s m g p - m d p n -” and “ś p n m - p r m s -” alternate between higher and lower intervals
- In the 22nd varisai, the pūrvāṅga of the first āvarta displays a non-linear svāra pattern, where the first and third svāra-s—such as “s” and “m” in “s m r p”—appear in close succession. It is also seen that the svāra-s “g” and “d” are deliberately omitted in the pūrvāṅga of both the first and second āvarta-s,
The second note in the pūrvāṅga of the āvarta becomes the first note in the second part in the ascent and descent.
- In the ascent, the pattern ‘m r p’ is repeated with madhyama śadja and tāra śadja.

- All the varisai-s in Section II reflect the influence of dātu swara phrases
- 21st and 22nd varisai-s have the common pattern ‘ś p n m p r m s’ in the descent.

Section–III:

Serial no.	Svarāvali
1.	s r g m - p d n ś - s , , , s , , , ś n d p - m g r s ś , , , ś , , ,
2.	s r g m - p d n ś - r , , , r , , , ś n d p - m g r s r , , , r , , ,
3.	s r g m - p d n ś - g , , , g , , , ś n d p - m g r s d , , , d , , ,
4.	s r g m - p d n ś - m , , , m , , , ś n d p - m g r s p , , , p , , ,

- Svара-s in second and fourth āvarta-s gives the Madhya sthāyi ṣaḍja and tāra sthāyi ṣaḍja respectively in the 1st varisai.
- Similarly, Rṣabha, Gāndhāra, Madhyama, Pañcama, Dhaivata occur in the second and fourth āvarta as dīrgha svара prayōga-s.

Serial no.	Svarāvali
5.	s r g m - p d n ś - ś , ś , p , p , ś n d p - m g r s s , s , p , p ,
6.	s r g m - p d n ś - ś , p , s , p , ś n d p - m g r s s , p , ś , p ,

- These varisai-s are similar to śruti svара exercises which come under the basic level exercises.
- They have ṣaḍja and pañcama with the combinations of madhyama sthāyi and tāra sthāyi.
- 5th varisai has ṣaḍja and pañcama with janṭa pattern by sustaining in the ascent and descent.
- Elongated svара-s are mentioned in all the varisai-s.

Serial no.	Svarāvaḷi
7.	s r g m - p d n ś - ś ś ś ś p p p p ś n d p - m g r s s s s s p p p p
8.	s r g m - p d n ś - ś ś p p s s p p ś n d p - m g r s s s p p ś ś p p

- Here the svāra-s, ṣaḍja and pañcama have the perpetuality with jaṅṭa pattern.
- 7th varisai has the quadruple pattern of ṣaḍja and pañcama.

Serial no.	Svarāvaḷi
9.	s r g m - p d n s - ś d p m s g d ś ś n d p - m g r s s g d p ś d p ś
10.	s r g m - p d n ś - ś , p , d n ś , ś n d p - m g r s s , p , m g s ,

- In the 9th varisai, ‘n’ is omitted giving various combinations of ‘s g d p’.
- In the 10th varisai , the 1st and 2nd dhṛuta-s have the dīrgha svāra-s omitting ‘r’.
- ‘s r g m p d n ś – ś n d p m g r s’ remains as a constantly used pattern before the diverging phrases in all the 3 sections.
- In section-I and section-II, ‘s r g m p d n s - ś n d p m g r s’ occurs in the second part of each āvarta.
- In the section -III, s r g m p d n s - ś n d p m g r s is given in the pūrvāṅga of each āvarta.
- The combinations of dāṭu, jaṅṭa and Sruti svāra exercises are seen in the varisai-s.

2. Heccusthāyi varisai-s:

Heccusthāyi varisai-s are given under two sections:

Section-I:

Serial no.	Heccusthāyi varisai
1.	s r g m - p d n ś r , , , ś , , , p d n ś - ṛ , ś n - d n ś ṛ - d p m p d n ś ṛ - ṛ ś ś n - ś ṛ ś n - d p m p - d n ś ṛ - ś ṛ ś n ś n d p - m g r s

2.	s r g m - p d n ś - r , , , ġ , , , p d n ś - ř ś n d - ř ř ś n d n ś ř - ř ġ ř ś - ś ř ř ś ś n d p d n ś ř - ġ ř ś n - ś n d p - m g r s
3.	s r g m - p d n ś ř , ġ , , , p d n ś - ř ř ś n - ś ř ġ ř - ś n d p p d n ś - ř ġ ř , ś , ř ś ś n d p - d n ś - ġ ř ś n - ś ř ř ř - ś n d p d n ś ř - ġ m ś ř - m ġ ř ś ś n d p - d n ś ř - ś n d p - ś n d p - m g r s
4.	s r g m - p d n ś - ř ġ m p̣ - m ś ř ś - ś ř ġ m - m ġ ř ś - ś ř ġ ř - ś n d p - d n ś ř - ġ ř ř ř - ś ř ġ ř - ś n d p - d n ś ř - ř ś ś n - ś n d p - m g r s

- There is no particular pattern given in the first section.

Section-II:

Serial no.	Heccusthāyi varisai
5.	s r g m - p d n ś - r , , , ś , , , ś n d n - ś ř ř ř - ś n d p - m g r s -
6.	s r g m - p d n ś - r , , , ġ , , , ś ř ġ ř - ś ř ś n - d n d p - m g r s -
7.	s r g m - p d n ś - ř , ġ , m , , , m ġ m ř - ġ ř ř ř - ś n d p - m g r s -
8.	s r g m - p d n ś - ř ġ m p̣ m ġ ř ġ ś ř ġ m - p̣ m ġ ř - ś n d p - m g r s -

- Heccusthāyi varisai-s are basically tāra sthāyi varisai-s.
- In the 1st dhṛta of every varisai, there is an increasing pattern of svara-s i.e., ‘r , , , ś , , ,’, ‘r , , , ġ , , ,’, ‘ř , ġ , m , , ,’ and ‘ř ġ m p̣’.
- The highest note in the above varisai-s is the tāra sthāyi pañcama and then it ends gradually by coming back to madhyasthāyi ṣaḍja.

3. Jaṅṭavarusalū:

They are divided into 2 sections.

Serial no.	Jaṅṭavarisai
1.	s s r r - g g m m - p p d d - n n ś ś - ś ś n n - d d p p - m m g g - r r s s -
2.	s s s s - r r r r - g g g g - m m m m - p p p p - d d d d - n n n n - ś ś ś ś -

	ś ś ś ś - n n n n - d d d d - p p p p - m m m m - g g g g - r r r r - s s s s -
3.	s s r r - g g m m - s s r r - g g m m - s s r r - g g m m - p p d d - n n ś ś - ś ś n n n - d d p p - ś ś n n n - d d p p - ś ś n n n - d d p p - m m g g - r r s s -

- Quadruple svāra-s are seen in the 2nd varisai.
- In the 3rd varisai, ‘s s r r – g g m m’ and ‘ś ś n n n - d d p p’ is repeated thrice in the ascent and descent.

Serial no.	Jaṅṭavarisai
4.	s s r r - g g m m - r r g g - m m p p - g g m m - p p d d - m m p p - d d n n - p p d d - n n ś ś - ś ś n n - d d p p - n n d d - p p m m - d d p p - m m g g - p p m m - g g r r - m m g g - r r s s -
5.	s s r r - s s r r - s s r r - g g m m - r r g g - r r g g - r r g g - m m p p - p p m m - p p m m - p p m m - g g r r - m m g g - m m g g - m m g g - r r s s -
6.	s s r r - g g r r - s s r r - g g m m - r r g g - m m g g - r r g g - m m p p - p p m m - g g m m - p p m m - g g r r - m m g g - r r g g - m m g g - r r s s -

- 5th varisai has the phrase ‘s s r r’ repeated thrice. Similarly, pūrvāṅga of the everyline is repeated thrice.

Section-II:

Serial no.	Jaṅṭa varisai
7.	s r r s - s r r g - r g g r - r g g m - g m m g - g m m p - m p p m - m p p d - p d d p - p d d n - d n n d - d n n ś - ś n n ś - ś n n d - n d d n - n d d p - d p p d - d p p m - p m m p - p m m g - m g g m - m g g r - g r r g - g r r s -
8.	s s s - r r r - g g - s s r r - g g m m - r r r - g g g - m m - r r g g - m m p p - p p p - m m m - g g - p p m m - g g r r - m m m - g g g - r r m m g g - r r s s -

- The palindrome patterns ‘s r r s’, ‘r g g r’, ‘g m m g’,..... ‘d n n d’ and ‘s n n s’, ‘n d d n’....’g r r g’ are seen in the 7th varisai.

Serial no.	Jaṅṭa varisai
9.	s , s - r , r g m - s s , r - r , g m - s s r , - g , g m - s s r r - g g m m - m , m - g , g r s - m m , g - g , r s - m m g , - r , r s - m m g g - r r s s -

- The elongated svāra-s occur in a pattern-1st & 3rd svāra, 2nd & 1st svāra and 3rd & 1st svāra i.e., ‘s , s r , r g m - s s , - r r , g m - s s r , - g , g m’.

Serial no.	Jaṅṭa varisai
10.	s r r g - g , r s - s r , g - s r g , - s , r g - s , r , - g g , r - g r s , - s ṅ ṅ ḍ - ḍ , ṅ s - s ṅ , ḍ - s ṅ ḍ , - s , ṅ ḍ - s , ṅ - ḍ ḍ , ṅ - ḍ ṅ s , -

- In the 10th jaṅṭa varisai, elongated svāra-s are given in a numerical pattern ‘2,3,1’ - ‘s r , g s r g , s , r g’.

4. Dāṭu varusalu:

Serial no.	Dāṭu varisai
1.	s g r m - s m g r - s m g m - p n d ś - ś d n p - ś p d n - ś p d p - m r g s -
2.	s g r m - s p m r - s m g r - g p d ś - ś d n p - ś p n m - ś p d n - d m g s -
3.	s g r p - s p m g - s m g p - s g r m - ś d n p - d m p g - p r g m - m r g s -
4.	s p m g - s m g r - s g r ṅ - s r g m - ś p d n - ś d n p - n m p g - m r g s -

- Different combinations of ‘s r g m’ and ‘ś n d p’ are given in all the varisai-s.
- In the 4th varisai, there is a decreasing pattern in the pūrvāṅga of the 1st āvarta - ‘s p m g - s m g r - |’, following the pattern ‘1-5-4-3 and 1-4-3-2’ respectively.
- Similarly, ‘ś p d n - ś d n p’ has the numerical pattern of notes- ‘8-5-6-7 - 8-6-5-7’

Serial no.	Dāṭu varisai
5.	s s m m - r p m g - s g r m - p d n ś - ś ś n d - d m p r - g d m g - m g s
6.	s g r m - g p m d - p n d ś - n ṛ ś ġ - ś d n p - d m p g - m r g s - ṇ ḍ r s -
7.	s m r p - m d p n - d ś n ṛ - d ġ ṛ ṁ - ś p n m - d g p r - m s g r - ṇ ḍ p s -
8.	s p , g - g d p m - s m , g - n d p g - s g , r - p n d p - s g r m - p n d ś - ś d , p - d m g r - g n , d - m g m d - n d , ś - n ṛ n d - n d m g - p g r s -

- Jaṅṭa prayōga is seen in the 5th varisai.
- 6th varisai has the alternative svara patterns ‘s g r m - g p m d - | p n d ś - | n ṛ ś ġ - ||’. Every 2nd note becomes 1st note in the next pattern and same happens in the descent – ‘ś d n p - d m p g - | m r g s - | ṇ ḍ r s - ||’
- In the 8th varisai, alternative svara combinations ‘s g r m – p n d s’.

5. Alaṅkarāmulu:

The text gives 7 alaṅkāra-s in Dhruva, Maṭhya, Rūpaka, Jhampa, Tripuṭa, Aṭa and Ēka in 5 jāti-s (Caturaśra, Tiśra, Miśra, Khaṇḍa and Saṅkīrṇa) making it as a total of 35 alaṅkāra-s.

Out of 35 alaṅkāra-s, the 5 alaṅkāra-s that are commonly practiced have been are tabulated below:

Caturaśra jāti Dhruvatāla - 14 akṣara kāla	Śrīkara: s r g m g r s r g r s r g m m g r s r g m g r g m g r s
Caturaśra jāti Maṭhya tāla - 10 akṣara kāla	Sama: s r g r s r s r g m m g r g m g m g r s
Caturaśra jāti Rūpakatāla- 6 akṣara kāla	Patti: s r s r g m r g r g m p
Tiśrajāti Tripuṭatāla-7 akṣara kāla	Ṣānta: s r g s r g m m g r m g r s
Caturaśra jāti Ēka tāla- 4 akṣara kāla	Māna: s r g m m g r s

The uncommon alaṅkara-s are:

Dhruva tāḷa	
Tiśrajāti - 11 Akṣara kāla	Maṇi : s r s g r s r g r g m m g m r g m g r g r s
Miśra jāti - 16 Akṣara kāla	Pūrṇa : s r g r s r g m g r s r s r g m s r g m r g m m g r g m g r g m g r g m r g m m g r s g r s
Khaṇḍajāti - 17 Akṣara kāla	Pramāṇa : s r g r s r g s r g m g r s r g m m g r g m g r m g r s r g m g r s
Saṅkīrṇajāti- 29 Akṣara kāla	Bhuvana: s r g m g r s r s s r s r g m g r s r g s r g r s s r g m m g r s r g m g m m g m g r s r g m g r m g r g m m g r s

- A numerical pattern is seen in the Bhuvana tāḷa - Saṅkīrṇajāti alaṅkāra –
s r g m - r g m.
1 2 3 4 - 2 3 4.

Maṭhya tāḷa	
Tiśra jāti – 8 Akṣarakāla	Sāra: s r s r g r g m m g m g r g r s
Miśra jāti –16 Akṣara kāla	udīrṇa: s r g m g r s r g s r g g r g m m g r s r g m g r m g r r g r s
Khaṇḍa jāti –12Akṣara kāla	Udaya: s r g r s s r s r r g m m g r g m m g m g g r s
Saṅkīrṇajāti –20Akṣara kāla	Rāva: s r g m g r s r g s r s r g r g s r g m m g r s r g m g r m g m g r g r m g r s

- Jaṅṭa prayōga is seen in the udīrṇa tāḷa - Miśra jāti and udaya tāḷa - Khaṇḍa jāti alaṅkāra-s.

Rūpaka tāḷa	
Tiśra jāti - 5 Akṣara kāla	Cakra: s r r g m m g g r s
Miśra jāti - 9 Akṣara kāla	Kula: s r g r s s r g m m g r g m m g r s
Khaṇḍajāti-7 Akṣarakāla	Rāja: s r r g m g m m g g r s r s
Saṅkīrṇa jāti -11 Akṣara kāla	Bindu: s r g r s s r g r g m m g r g m m g r g r s

- Jaṅṭa prayōga is seen in the Cakra tāḷa - Tiśra jāti alaṅkāra ‘s r r g m - r g g m p.....’

Jhampa tāḷa	
Tiśra jāti - 6 Akṣara kāla	Kadamba: s r g r g m m g r g r s
Caturaśrajāti- 7 Akṣara kāla	Madura: s r g m r g m m g r s g r s
Miśra jāti - 10 Akṣara kāla	Sura: s r g m g r s r g m m g r s r g m g r s
Khaṇḍajāti - 8 Akṣara kāla	Caṇa: s r g m g r g m m g r s r g r s
Saṅkīrṇa jāti-12Akṣara kāla	Kara: s r g m g r s r g r g m m g r s r g m g r g r s

- There is a numerical pattern ‘123- 234- 345...’ in Kadamba tāḷa - Tiśrajāti alaṅkāra.
- There is an influence of Yati in the Sura tāḷa – Miśrajāti alaṅkāra with the pattern ‘s r g m g r s’.

Tripuṭa tāḷa	
Caturaśra jāti- 4 Akṣara kāla	Ādi: s r g m g r g m m g r s r g r s
Miśra jāti – 11 Akṣara kāla	Līla: s r g m s r g s r g m m g r s m g r m g r s
Khaṇḍa jāti – 9 Akṣara kāla	Duṣkara: s r g r g s r g m m g r g r m g r s
Saṅkīrṇajāti -13Akṣarakāla	Bhōga: s r g m s r s r g s r g m m g r s m g m g r m g r s

- The svāra-s are given consecutively in the Līla tāḷa - Miśra jāti alaṅkāra having first and last parts as common phrases.
- There is a numerical pattern ‘1234-12-123-1234’ in the Bhōgi tāḷa - Saṅkīrṇa jāti alaṅkāra where the first part and the last part remain common.

Aṭa tāḷa	
Caturśrajāti-12 Akṣara kāla	Lēkha: s r g m m g r s s r g m m g r s s r g m m g r s
Tiśra jāti- 10 Akṣara kāla	Gupta: s r g g r s s r g m m g r r g m m g r s
Miśrajāti- 18Akṣarakāla	Lōya: s r g s r g m s r g m g r s s r g m m g r m g r s m g r s r g m m g r s
Khaṇḍajāti-14 Akṣarakāla	Vidaḷa: s r g s r r g m g m s r g m m g r m g g r s r s m g r s
Saṅkīrṇajāti- 22Akṣara kāla	Dhīra: s r g r s r g m g r g m g r s r g r s r g m m g r g m g r s r g r s r g m g r g m g r s

- The palindrome pattern is observed in the Lēkha tāḷa-Caturaśrajāti and GuptaTāḷa -Tiśra jāti alaṅkāra-s with the pattern ‘s r g m | m g r s | s r g m ||’ and ‘s r g | g r s |’ respectively.

Ēka tāḷa	
Tiśrajāti-3 Akṣara kāla	Sudha: s r g g r s
Miśra jāti – 7 Akṣara kāla	Rāga: s r g s r g m m g r m g r s
Khaṇḍa jāti – 5 Akṣara kāla	Rata: s r r g m m g g r s
Saṅkīrṇa jāti-9 Akṣara kāla	Vasu: s r g m g r r g m m g r s r g g r s

Observations:

- Saṅgīta Pradāyini is an early music publication in telugu language which covers both theoretical and practical aspects.
- The Index mentions ‘32 Tāḷa alaṅkāra-s’, which could be a scribble error as body of the content provides the description of ‘35 Tāḷa alaṅkāra-s.
- The authors have quoted sloka-s and incorporated some of the musical aspects from ‘Saṅgīta Ratnākara’ of Śāraṅgadēva, in Nāda prakaraṇa, Svāra prakaraṇa and Rāga prakaraṇa at the beginning of the Lakṣaṇa saṅgraha, explaining the concepts - Saṅgīta, Svāra, Nāda and so on.
- The Rāga Māḷavagauḷa is specified for usage in Svarāvaḷi, Heccusthāyi varusalu, Jaṇṭa varusalu, Dāṭu varusalu and Alaṅkāra-s.
- At the beginning of the Svarāvaḷi, tri-kāla-s i.e., Viḷamba, Madhyama and Dhṛta kāla-s are mentioned by taking the first varisai as an example.
- Different sections of the varisai-s are given with a set of patterns that are generally not seen in today’s practice lessons.
- The names of the tāḷa-s are mentioned for every alaṅkāra along with the jāti and akṣarakāla.
- The Tāḷa names given in ‘Saṅgīta Pradāyini’ are also mentioned in the earlier publication, ‘Gāyaka pārijātam’ of Taccūru Śingarācāryulu & Taccūru Aḷaha Śingarācāryulu(1877).
- However, a later publication, Gāna Vidyā Saṅjīvinī of C.Tirumalaiah Naiḍu (1896) mentions the names of Sapta tāḷa-s-Indranīla, Mahāvajra, Nirdōṣa, Sīra, Kōkila, Āvarta,

Sadānanda which are set to be taken from the Alaṅkāra prakaraṇa of ‘Saṅgīta Pārijāta’ of Ahōbala, as per the information given in the preface.

- Miśrajāti Jhampa tāḷa and Khaṇḍa jāti Aṭa tāḷa alaṅkāra-s are mentioned with the svāra-s, ‘s r g m g r s | r g m || and s r g s r | r g m g m | s r g m || respectively but these are replaced by ‘s r g s r s r | g | m , ||’ and ‘s r , g , | s , r g , | m , m , ||’ in the present day usage.
- Some of the varisai-s can be incorporated into the manōdharma aspects such as Tāna with the combinations:

$$8 \text{ svāra-s} = 5+3 - s r g m p + s r g$$

Tā.nam.ta+ nam..

$$6 \text{ svāra-s} = 3+3 - s r g + r g m$$

tā...+ nam..

$$5 \text{ svāra-s} = \text{a) } 2+3 - s r + s r g$$

tā..+nam..

$$\text{b) } 3+2 - s r g + s r$$

tā....+ nam.

- This combination of patterns also benefits a musician by incorporating the methods and developing an idea of presenting Kalpanasvāra.

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